

EPIC-SHIFT: Data Management Plan

Deliverable 1.1

Reviewed by	Organization
Maria Gomes Fernandes	NH

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
DEFINITIONS.....	4
EPIC-SHIFT COLLABORATORS.....	5
EPIC-SHIFT OVERVIEW.....	5
DATA SUMMARY	8
FAIR DATA	12
MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA.....	12
MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE.....	12
MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	14
MAKING DATA RE-USABLE.....	15
ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	15
DATA SECURITY.....	16
ETHICS	17

EPIC-SHIFT

Funded by
the European Union

Project no. Grant Agreement 101181470

Project acronym: EPIC-SHIFT

Project title: Securing Holistic and Impactful Food Systems Transformation with Novel Foods based on alternative proteins

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-01

Start date of project: 1.11.2024

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable title: Data Management Plan

Date of deliverable: 30.04.2025 -- 1.10.2025

Deliverable Lead Partner: ULUND

Dissemination level: Public

Executive Summary

This plan details the management of data and metadata collected, handled and generated under EPIC-SHIFT. It highlights how data will be stored and processed, as well as the different types of data collected by project partners. The EPIC-SHIFT project is dedicated to creating a lasting impact on the food system through innovative research and strategic communication, ensuring that our knowledge base and the resulting technological advances are accessible and beneficial to all stakeholders.

Definitions

NFAP-	Novel Foods based on Alternative Protein sources - proteins derived from insect, fungi, bacteria, micro and macro algae and agriculture and aquaculture by-products
DMP-	Data Management Plan
TEA-	Techno-Economic Analysis
LCA-	Life Cycle Assessment
S-LCA-	Social Life Cycle Assessment
DOI-	Digital Object Identifier
WP-	Work Package
IPR-	Intellectual Property Rights
DMR-	Data Management Repository
DPO-	Data Protection Officer
ARK-	Archival Resource Key
FAIR-	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDPR-	General Data Protection Regulation

EPIC-SHIFT Collaborators

Number	Short name	Legal name	Country
1	ULUND	LUNDS UNIVERSITET	PT
2	UOXF	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK
3	UH	HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	FI
4	DTU	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DK
5	CNTA	CENTRO NACIONAL DE TECNOLOGIA Y SEGURIDAD ALIMENTARIA	ES
6	ACG-RC	AMERIKANIKO KOLLEGIO ELLADOS, KENTRO EREVNAS	EL
7	ECOINNOVAZIONE	ECOINNOVAZIONE SRL	IT
8	SAFE	SAFE FOOD ADVOCACY EUROPE	BE
9	EIT FOOD	EIT FOOD CLC NORTH-EAST SP ZOO	PL
10	NH	STICHTING NEW HARVEST NETHERLANDS	NL
11	SHAKE-UP	SHAKE-UP FACTORY	FR
12	FOOD+i	ASOCIACION CLUSTER FOOD+I	ES
13	ATOVA	ATOVA REGULATORY CONSULTING	ES
14	PURATOS	PURATOS NV	BE
15	DANONE	Danone Global Research & Innovation Center	FR
16	INNOMY	INNOMY BIOTECH SL	ES
17	POSEIDONA	POSEIDONADA SL	ES
18	DLG	DLG EV	DE

EPIC-SHIFT Overview

Funded by HORIZON EUROPE-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-01-7. Designed as a think-tank and adopting Food Systems Thinking approach, EPIC-SHIFT will provide a multidimensional impact assessment (LCA, SLCA, TEA) of various novel foods that are based on alternative sources of proteins (NFAP - from protein type to product level) at scale complemented with the necessary recommendations for food environments, marketing, regulatory approval, infrastructure and investment needed to support long-term market growth. EPIC-SHIFT integrated scenario analysis will further result in decision support tools that will inform policy and decision-making about the trajectories to achieve the sustainable integration of NFAP in the EU diets

ensuring resource efficiency, food security and nutrition within a framework of just transition for all food system actors.

The project is structured into eight work packages (WPs) which are interconnected. Table 1 indicates the title and lead participant of each WP.

Table 1: Work package description for the eight work packages that collectively comprise EPIC-SHIFT, as well as an indication of the acronym of lead participant for each work package.

Work Package	Title	Lead
1	Project management and coordination	ULUND
2	Alternative proteins knowledge hub	ULUND
3	Economic impact	ACG-RC
4	Multidimensional impact assessment	UH
5	Social considerations and social implications of a widespread shift to diets with NFAP	CNTA
6	Integrated impact assessment	UOXF
7	Communication, dissemination and open science	EIT FOOD
8	Ethics	ULUND

For the EPIC-SHIFT project to achieve the intended impact, each WP has planned out a suite of deliverables which can be found along with a short description of the deliverable, the lead partner and the month expected as deadline for that deliverable in Table 2.

Table 2: Deliverable list for EPIC-SHIFT, along with short description of each deliverable, dedicated work package, as well as the lead institution and month of completion for each deliverable.

Deliverabl No	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
D1.1	1st version of Data management plan (DMP)	WP1	1 - ULUND	DMP — Data Management Plan	PU - Public	6
D1.2	2nd version of Data management plan (DMP)	WP1	1 - ULUND	DMP — Data Management Plan	PU - Public	18
D1.3	3rd version of Data management plan (DMP)	WP1	1 - ULUND	DMP — Data Management Plan	PU - Public	36
D1.4	First Report of Ethical Advisor	WP1	1 - ULUND	R — Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	18
D1.5	Second Report of Ethical Advisor	WP1	1 - ULUND	R — Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	36
D2.1	1st version of Watch Platform	WP2	11 - SHAKE-UP	R — Document, report	PU - Public	9

D2.2	1st version of Food systems interactive visualisation tool	WP2	1 - ULUND	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	12
D2.3	2nd version of Watch Platform	WP2	11 - SHAKE-UP	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D2.4	2nd version of Food systems interactive visualisation tool	WP2	1 - ULUND	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	30
D3.1	NFAP Market projections according to techno-functional properties	WP3	5 - CNTA	R — Document, report	PU - Public	15
D3.2	Optimal NFAP marketing strategies	WP3	6 - ACG-RC	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24
D3.3	Pricing perspectives of NFAP	WP3	2 - UOXF	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24
D3.4	Recommendations for investments in NFAP	WP3	11 - SHAKE-UP	R — Document, report	PU - Public	30
D4.1	LCA of NFAP	WP4	3 - UH	R — Document, report	PU - Public	28
D4.2	TEA of NFAP	WP4	4 - DTU	R — Document, report	PU - Public	28
D4.3	S-LCA of NFAP	WP4	7 - ECOINNOVAZIONE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	28
D5.1	Recommendations for Novel Foods regulatory approval process	WP5	13 - ATOVA	R — Document, report	PU - Public	12
D5.2	Nutritional and health impacts of NFAP in diets	WP5	2 - UOXF	R — Document, report	PU - Public	20
D5.3	Opportunities and challenges for farmers and aquafarmers	WP5	18 - DLG	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24
D5.4	Market adoption report	WP5	5 - CNTA	R — Document, report	PU - Public	30
D6.1	Systems modelling of NFAP impact	WP6	1 - ULUND	R — Document, report	PU - Public	34
D6.2	Dietary challenges and opportunities of NFAP	WP6	2 - UOXF	R — Document, report	PU - Public	34
D6.3	White paper harnessing NFAP impact to further societal goals. White paper discussing the project key outcomes, needed measures for NFAP industry and identification of knowledge gaps	WP6	1 - ULUND	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D7.1	Project website	WP7	9 - EIT FOOD	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU - Public	4
D7.2	1st version of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	WP7	9 - EIT FOOD	R — Document, report	PU - Public	6
D7.3	Policy recommendations	WP7	8 - SAFE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	33
D7.4	Exploitation strategy and funding watch	WP7	9 - EIT FOOD	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D7.5	2nd version of Communication,	WP7	9 - EIT FOOD	R — Document, report	PU - Public	18

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

	Dissemination and Exploitation Plan					
D7.6	3rd version of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	WP7	9 - EIT FOOD	R — Document, report	PU - Public	20
D8.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	WP8	1 - ULUND	ETHICS	SEN - Sensitive	1

Data Summary

EPIC-SHIFT will reuse existing data to fulfil our research objectives whenever the needed data is available. The motivation for collecting and generating data under EPIC-SHIFT lies in the need to understand the current technical landscape of NFAP, as well as consumer perception, ethical challenges, and techno-economic considerations that are required to be analysed for the industry to be viable from a societal perspective.

The following table (Table 3) defines the purpose of data collected and generated under each WP, as well as keywords defined for each task under the different WPs.

Table 3: Purpose of data collection for work packages 1-7 and respective keywords.

Work Package	Purpose of data	Keywords
1	Data collected and generated will be in the form of reports and management plans that serve to inform all partners on the use of data under EPIC-SHIFT and to ensure management of innovation outputs throughout the project’s lifetime	Coordination, Knowledge, Data Management, Innovation management,
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data will be collected and generated to better understand and engage with NFAP stakeholders and other relevant projects. - Data will be collected and generated to understand the environmental, technological and socioeconomic requirements to meet the impact goals of the 	Multistakeholder Engagement, Stakeholder Mapping, Knowledge hub, food systems thinking approach

	projects and be able to provide a NFAP knowledge hub.	
3	Data will be collected and generated for the assessment of NFAP market potential and market dynamics.	NFAP market potential, market dynamics
4	<p>-Data will be collected and generated for baseline analysis and hotspot screening, process design and assessment</p> <p>- Data will be collected and generated for the purpose of establishing outputs such as environmental and social life-cycle assessment, and techno-economic assessment that help determining the maturity and potential impact of the NFAP industry by understanding costs, processes and supply methods.</p>	Key Performance Indicators, Bioreactor, Bioprocess, Techno Economic Assessment, Environmental and Social Life-Cycle Assessment
5	<p>- Data will be collected and generated for the purpose of nutritional considerations and health benefits.</p> <p>- Data will be collected to for the impact assessment of the regulatory framework on market access of NFAP.</p> <p>- Data will be collected and generated to better understand and engage with NFAP stakeholders, particularly consumers and current agriculture and aquaculture actors. Additionally, data will serve to evaluate ethical impacts of NFAP.</p>	Food Safety, Nutrition, Regulatory Assessment, Regulatory Framework, Consumer Acceptance, Ethical Considerations
6	Data will be collected and generated for the purpose of system dynamics modelling and integrated impact assessment	System Dynamic Modelling, Integrated Scenario Analysis
7	Data will be collected and compiled from adjacent	Communication, Dissemination,

	projects to improve EPIC-SHIFT's scientific dissemination plan and activities.	Data exploitation, Open Science, Open Access Research.
--	--	--

The existing datasets that will be reused include data on stakeholders, ethical issues, data on consumer perceptions and drivers of acceptance, on value chain actors, governance and business models, as well as data on the current farmer and aquafarmer industry (actors, business models, etc.) to accomplish certain outputs such as those from WP5 in Task 5.4, which include reports, roundtables and letter of recommendations.

The project will generate and re-use both qualitative and quantitative data collected from various sources such as reports, observations, historical records, scientific publications, grey literature such as media reports, policy documents, databases (including databases for LCA and Social LCA) and interviews, surveys (including internal surveys with project partners), questionnaires and workshops. The data will include experimental numerical and observational data, images, and text. The data will be organized into an existing, FAIR, repository e.g. Zenodo for non-structured data. Other sources of data that might be collected during EPIC-SHIFT will be subsequently updated in the following DMP reviews planned henceforth.

Data generation or re-use serves the purpose of supporting the objectives of the project, which include conducting a LCA and a S-LCA, performing tests regarding the structure and behaviour of the model developed, simulating explorative scenarios of different transition pathways, and enhancing stakeholder capacity to analyse dynamic and complex sustainability issues in the transition to a sustainable future in the NFAP sector.

To successfully develop the deliverables set out for the EPIC-SHIFT project, data and metadata will be collected and generated in a plurality of formats (when possible, open formats will be used over proprietary ones), which are described in Table 4 for each WP along with the expected data size. Other software will be used to generate and collect data to accomplish certain

milestones, including Adobe Acrobat Reader, Stella Architect, Phyton, R, SPSS, SuperPro Design, GraphPad, AutoCAD, JMP, MIRO, Design-Expert, OpenLCA, PSILCA, Simapro and platforms focused on sensory analysis and consumer studies (e.g., MundoSabor, Compusense, SurveyLab). Overall, the data size for both collected and generated data within EPIC-SHIFT, including raw data from software mentioned in the paragraph above and data described in Table 4, is expected to be under 10TB.

Table 4: Expected format and size of data collected and generated under each work package of EPIC-SHIFT

	Text	Image	Tabular	Video	Expected Size
	doc/docx, pdf, ods, odt, txt, xls/xlsx, html	tiff, png, jpeg	csv	mp4, wmv/wma	
WP1	x	x			10GB
WP2	x	x	x	x	10GB
WP3	x	x	x	x	100GB
WP4	x		x	x	10GB
WP5	x	x			10GB
WP6	x	x	x		10GB
WP7	x	x	x	x	10GB
WP8	x				100MB

The data produced under EPIC-SHIFT will likely be of interest to the following groups:

- NFAP community.
- Academic researchers.
- For-profit entities such as start-ups and SMEs.
- EU policy makers and legislators.
- Scientific organizations, non-profit organizations, non-governmental organizations, think thanks, contract-research organizations, contract manufacturing organizations.
- General public

FAIR Data

Making data Findable, including provisions for metadata

Scientific data generated under EPIC-SHIFT such as review and research articles, as well as their associated datasets that include figures and tables will be identified by persistent identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for publications and ORCID identifiers for researchers.

Other data outputs from the project including reports, white-papers and other grey literature, as well as stakeholder maps and videos will be ensured to be findable using various mechanisms, including having them stored in public data repositories such as Zenodo, and in certain cases Vimeo, as well as within the project's website through an identifiable URL. The project's partners will also be attributing tags and keywords related with the industry to its data outputs to improve its traceability. Should there be a need to assign a standardized persistent identifier to datasets and metadata that do not comprise peer-reviewed scientific articles, an Archival Resource Key (ARK) will be used for its compatibility with a wide range of content types.

Rich metadata will be provided to facilitate discovery. Standardized metadata frameworks will be used, and metadata will include information about the data's origin, format, content, and usage. Disciplinary or general standards such as the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) principles will be followed. Metadata will be offered in a way that it can be harvested and indexed to enhance discoverability and accessibility.

Making data Accessible

The DMP will be deposited in a trusted repository such as DMPOnline. Appropriate arrangements will be explored with the identified repository. The repository will ensure that the data is assigned an identifier, and it will resolve the identifier to a digital object. Pre-prints of the reports and manuscripts will be deposited on open data repositories such as Zenodo or

BioRxiv allowing for wide access without hinder publication on high impact peer reviewed journals. Open Research Europe publication platform or other open access publishers will be used. The DMP will be updated on a Data Management Repository (DMR), also deposited on a public repository with links and identifiers for all the research outputs and information on the database where the cured data is deposited. The data will be stored in a unique database on a European server to make sure that the European laws apply and will be accompanied by metadata that will help finding and using them. All data will be also stored on a back-up server to prevent a possible loss. The data will be stored and curated under the responsibility of the project coordinator and the Data Protection Officer (DPO) from the coordinator's institution. The costs for data curation and preservation will be undertaken by each partner.

The results of the project as previously established in the Grant Agreement will be made available, including both the data analytics source code, and the datasets origin, to facilitate reproducibility. While the datasets needed to achieve the project's objectives will be accessible, sensitive data regarding contact information, interviews and inputs from external stakeholders will be collected to generate certain deliverables in WP2, WP3, WP5 and WP7. In these cases, data will only be shared within consortium partners under confidentiality, such as for the stakeholder maps generated under WP2. In certain cases, namely for deliverables of WP4 and WP7, quantitative and qualitative data from industry stakeholders will have improved accessibility by guaranteeing full anonymity of registered data and using pooled data presentation strategies. Furthermore, an analysis of sensitive data will be performed to avoid unexpected data leakage. The consortium will also apply the requirement to adhere to the Open Research Data Pilot. If there is the need to apply embargo, its duration will be minimized to ensure prompt availability of data. Other data related with an institution's intellectual property and trade secret processes will not be shared for confidential reasons.

Data regarding scientific findings and other deliverables set out as per Grant Agreement will be published for free access in platforms where Open Access Research is prioritized. Fees to support publishing and storage of data for free access have been accounted for in the Grant Agreement and shall be covered by designated partners to allow open access to data stemming from their research. Under EPIC-SHIFT, common and user-friendly software that require no user guidance documents will be prioritized as the chosen tools for data access. The data produced in the project can be used by third parties, including researchers, non-profit and for-profit institutions and organizations. Data will become more useful at the end of the project where a complete set of data can be presented and utilized in developing further research or actions by stakeholders.

Making data Interoperable

Due to the nature of the data collected and its expected impact, EPIC-SHIFT will ensure data interoperability by using vocabularies commonly used for the metadata within the datasets generated. The use of the English language in data generated will primarily ensure its interoperability. In addition, the project will standardize data capture and presentation, both for experimental scientific metadata and qualitative data.

While new project-specific keywords and ontologies may arise through the duration of EPIC-SHIFT, the project will thoroughly indicate and communicate these by updating the project's public deliverables with specific terms, keywords and ontologies to ensure data re-use and improve its reach.

Metadata generated by EPIC-SHIFT according to project deliverables is intended to be exchanged and integrated seamlessly through different internal and external partners as well as the public and therefore will be collected and generated in compliance with relevant regional and European-wide data protection regulations.

Making data Re-usable

Datasets generated under EPIC-SHIFT, as previously mentioned, will be stored in public databases such as Zenodo, BioRxiv and DMRs, which will improve the re-usability of the datasets generated. Scientific data re-usability will be further improved by establishing and publishing standard operating procedures for data collection practices.

The data will be stored in a unique database on a European server to make sure that the European laws apply and will be accompanied by metadata that will help finding and using them. All data will be also stored on a back-up server to prevent a possible loss. The data will be stored and curated under the responsibility of the project coordinator and project DPO. CC licenses in place will allow data reuse in line with operating under Open Access guidelines, as set out in the Grant Agreement.

Allocation of Resources

Costs of collecting and preserving long-term data were accounted for in the project's budget. Whenever possible, data preservation and accessibility will be ensured by using free data repositories and services such as Zenodo and Microsoft Teams, the latter being used for internal communication, data sharing and storage of raw data.

EPIC-SHIFT has allocated resources for achieving principles for FAIR data which include working hours by researchers and managers to collect and accurately manage data generated under the project. Additionally, costs for collecting and generating data, namely scientific data in open access journals has been accounted for in the budget. Each work package leader will be responsible for ensuring data preservation during the project in safe, long-term storage repositories. Data management will be led by ULUND which will ensure data validation from collection to storage and handling.

For the duration of EPIC-SHIFT, the partners that collect or generate data under a given WP are responsible for registering data, validating it in coordination with ULUND, treating its metadata, maintaining and preserving data, as well as uploading it into open access repositories. All WP leaders and associated partners should be consulted before publishing data concerning a given result. Moreover, all partners must follow the necessary procedures - as highlighted in this document - to make FAIR data which is safely stored and compliant with local and European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) directives.

Data Security

The data will be stored in a unique database on a European server to make sure that the European laws apply and will be accompanied by metadata that will help finding and using them. All data will be also stored on a back-up server to prevent a possible loss. The data will be stored and curated under the responsibility of the project coordinator and project DPO. The costs for data curation and preservation will be undertaken by each partner.

Raw data and identifiable data used by EPIC-SHIFT partners to achieve the project's milestones (e.g., data from interviews and multi-stakeholder mapping) will be stored responsibly in folders and repositories with restricted access on a need-to-know basis, including Microsoft Teams.

WP-specific personal data that will be collected to achieve project milestones and will be compliant with GDPR include:

- WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP7 will collect names, surnames, addresses, email addresses, phone numbers, name of institution and work position from potential stakeholders through surveys and newsletter subscribers, which will be stored on Microsoft SharePoint. In instances where surveys with personal data are carried, it will include pseudonymization before data analysis.

General guidelines will be followed to strengthen data security of EPIC-SHIFT, including storage of data in at least two different locations to steer clear of data loss, as well as limiting the use of USB drives for data storage and ensuring a standardized labelling of data to avoid data loss and so that large datasets can be thoroughly analysed by different stakeholders and partners.

Ethics

EPIC-SHIFT will fully comply with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26.04.2016 on the protection of natural persons with regards to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). It replaces the Data Protection Directive national transpositions and is directly applicable in all EU member states.

EPIC-SHIFT will comply with Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council 18 of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy.

Informed consent for data sharing will be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, and long-term preservation of the data will be addressed prior to questionnaires. In those instances, EU GDPR directives will be followed and informed consent for data sharing will be enquired prior to collecting data deemed identifiable.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	06.05.2025	Initial version